

**MODERNIZATION OF THE CURRENT TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS
OF CABLE PRODUCTION OF NATIONAL HOLDINGS LLC BY
ENSURING INCREASED SMOOTHNESS OF WIRE TENSION**

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Annotation. The article presents the results of modernizing the current technological process of cable production of NATIONAL HOLDINGS LLC by ensuring an increase in the smoothness of wire tension. It is shown that the use of a soft start device will significantly reduce the harmful dynamic effects on the engine and drive mechanism, will provide a significant increase in the service life of electric motors and actuators, and will also increase the service life of expensive equipment - dies, and will also reduce the level of copper waste.

Key words: asynchronous electric drive, frequency converter, dynamic mode, electromechanical system, electric drive control system.

Аннотация. В статье приводятся результаты по модернизации действующего технологического процесса кабельного производства ООО «NATIONAL HOLDINGS» за счет обеспечения повышения плавности

натяжения проволоки. Показано, что применение устройства плавного пуска позволит существенно уменьшить вредные динамические воздействия на двигатель и приводной механизм, обеспечит значительное увеличение срока эксплуатации электродвигателей и исполнительных устройств, а также увеличит срок службы дорогостоящего оборудования – фильеров, а также обеспечит снижение уровня отходов меди.

Ключевые слова: асинхронный электропривод, частотный преобразователь, динамический режим, электромеханическая система, система управления электроприводом.

Аннотация. Maqolada sim tarangligining silliqiligini oshirishni ta'minlash orqali NATIONAL HOLDINGS MChJ korxonasida kabel ishlab chiqarishning joriy texnologik jarayonini modernizatsiya qilish natijalari keltirilgan. Yumshoq ishga tushirish moslamasidan foydalanish orqali yuritma motori va qo'zg'alish mexanizmiga zararli dinamik ta'sirni sezilarli darajada kamaytirishi, elektr motori va ishchi organining ishlash muddatini sezilarli darajada oshirishi, shuningdek, qimmatbaho uskunalар - fileralarning ishlash muddatini oshirishi, shuningdek, mis chiqindilari darajasini pasaytirilishi ko'rsatilgan...

Калит сўзлар: асинхрон электр юритма, частота ўзгарткичи, динамик режим, электромеханик тизим, электр юритмани бошқариш тизими.

In the world, special attention is paid to solving problems in the development of power semiconductor converter technology based on current converters, which are widely used in various industrial fields, their rational use with high accuracy in maintaining energy parameters, increasing operational reliability and increasing service life. Currently, in developed countries, “...more than 60% of generated electricity passes through semiconductor converters. By using power electronics systems up to the world level, it will be possible to save 12-15% of generated electricity” [1]. In this regard, special attention is paid to increasing the energy efficiency of valve converters based on current converters for various purposes, designed to provide the required power supply for energy facilities with increased

requirements for the quality of energy consumed and the reliability of energy resources [2].

There is no doubt that to solve the above problems is the development and implementation of various measures to modernize the technological process of cable production.

This article presents the results of modernization of the current technological process of cable production of NATIONAL HOLDINGS LLC by ensuring an increase in the smoothness of wire tension. This proposed technical solution will allow, by ensuring increased smoothness of wire tension and drawing, to significantly reduce harmful dynamic effects on the engine and drive mechanism, significantly increase the service life of electric motors and actuators, and also increase the service life of expensive equipment and reduce the level of copper waste.

Currently, there is no longer any doubt about the advantage of soft starting of electric motors over direct starting or various types of soft starting simulations, such as switching from star to delta, using an autotransformer, etc. [3].

Thyristor starting devices (TPU), or, as they are also called, soft start devices (SPDs), designed to control the starting modes and stopping modes of three-phase low-voltage asynchronous motors (IM) with a squirrel-cage rotor, are becoming widespread all over the world.

Starting asynchronous squirrel-cage motors by direct connection to the network is usually accompanied by a large starting current, several times the rated value. The motor torque during direct starting can also reach values significantly exceeding the nominal one. This leads to heavy loads both on the driven mechanism and on the supply network. A number of mechanisms require a smooth increase or decrease in engine torque during acceleration, deceleration or braking. To solve this problem, special starting devices are used to reduce the starting current and motor torque.

The use of UPP allows:

- 1) limit peak mechanical loads of both the engine and the mechanism;
- 2) perform a soft, shock-free start;

- 3) limit starting current;
- 4) improve power factor;
- 5) save energy when the engine is running in unloaded mode;
- 6) eliminate current peaks during switching;
- 7) in some cases, exclude the use of sliding clutches and fluid couplings.

At the NATIONAL HOLDINGS LLC enterprise, it was proposed to use soft starters (SPD) of the JKSSS series. Thanks to numerous studies and recent developments, a modern series of JKSSS soft starters for electric motors, made using thyristors, has emerged. The compact design with optimal arrangement of components (400A cabinet width is only 762 mm) is convenient and safe to maintain and operate.

The JKSSS series for starting and protecting asynchronous, synchronous electric motors and wound-rotor motors is available for voltages up to 6.6 kV (for voltages of 10 kV and higher, they are manufactured individually to order).

Fig.1. Soft start device (SPD) of the JKSSS series: a) appearance; b) electrical diagram

Soft starters provide controlled functions: protection against abnormal conditions and diagnostics both during start-up and in operating mode, shockless start - start with a reduced starting torque with the most favorable mode for the drive mechanism, stop mode. Shockless starting is carried out by applying voltage to the engine according to an exponential law. In this case, the starting torque can be reduced by approximately 10 times compared to direct starting. A controlled start also refers to a complex start (delayed start), when the start time is adjusted within 0.2 - 60 s, and a start with a current cut-off, wherein the starting currents during the start-up do not exceed the specified cut-off current. In the starting mode with current cut-off, the values of starting currents (cut-off currents) can be set within the limits $I_{\text{start}} = I_{\text{nom}} \div 6 I_{\text{nom}}$, where I_{nom} is the rated current of the motor.

The overall result of using the soft starter is to increase the reliability of the electric drive and installation.

The developed modernization of drawing technology through the use of soft starters made it possible to:

- reducing the level of copper waste (by 8%);
- increasing the service life of expensive equipment - natural diamond dies on average (by 5%);
- machine time extended (by 12%);
- the number of shifts of operation of process equipment without refilling it has been increased by an average of 1.2 times.

At the same time, the main task to be solved was to improve the operational parameters of the current-carrying core of cable and wire products by increasing the smoothness of the technological process and reducing wire breakage, controlling its parameters taking into account the drawing object - the wire operating in the working units and mechanisms, the electromechanical system of their interaction with the technological tool.

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